

Banksy's Dismaland: A brief analysis of emotions through design

Adriana Galli Velho¹
adrianagallivelho@gmail.com

Viviane Peçaiques de Mello¹
vivianepecaibes@gmail.com

Gabriela Zubaran de Azevedo Pizzato¹
gabrielapizzato@gmail.com

¹Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

Abstract This article does the relation between the approaches of emotion and Emotional Design with the artistic intervention called Dismaland, created by Banksy in association with other contemporary artists. In this art project there was a clear intention of stimulate people that enjoyed the park on emotions that make them think over social and cultural values. It's possible to relate Emotional Design with the established project, because there is a logic in demonstrate that emotion is a result of stimulus that people are lead to have about the contact with products and services, resulting on evaluations established on this context of information processes revealed on this experience. It's possible to recognize that, even leading to pleasant and unpleasent emotions, Dismaland fulfilled its intention on causing a reflection and social critic to current lifestyle and culture.

Keywords *Emotional design, Emotion, Design, Banksy, Dismaland*

Introduction

People are frequently boosted by stimulus that make them respond, in general, in an evaluative way, to the environment where they are inserted. This answer is related to interpretations that the brain makes and leads the body to respond in a physical way. As he develops the concept of emotion, Damasio (2000) resorts on respected authors like Willian James (1884) who, while analyzing the construct of other respected authors like Shakespeare, in the works *Otelo* and *Hamlet*, relates emotion to literary narratives and the way it can explore, besides the body, the cognitive sense of such concept. In this aspect, Damasio (2000, p. 74) defines:

Emotions are adaptations that integrate mechanisms which through the organisms regulate life, sometimes in a specific reaction to a situation, sometimes in the regulation of the inner state of the individual, whose job is to help the organism to preserve life.

It is necessary to address an assertion about emotion that, many times, causes misinterpretations. There is a difference between the concepts of emotion and feeling and other types of affective expressions. Emotion is defined through the understanding of the elements that compose the emotional state. (Scherer, 2005).

The elements that compose the emotional state are not related in a disconnected way, for this relation to happen, experience and stimulus make this interaction possible, which Damasio (1996) describes as “*not a luxury*”, but a mental process of evaluation that is voluntary and not automatic:

The reactions to this broad spectrum of stimulus and situations can be filtered through a process of weighted deliberation. This reflexive and evaluative filter presents the possibility of variations on the

proportions and intensity of the pre-established emotion patterns and produces, as a result, a modulation in the basic machinery of emotions. (Damasio, 1996)

These emotional reactions create responses on the physical state of the individual that translates on pleasant and unpleasent sensations that many times can lead a person to keep away or approach the provocative stimulus, as Damasio (1996) comment:

If it didn't exist the possibility to feel the states of body, that are inherently destined to be painful or pleasant, there wouldn't be suffering or happiness, desire or mercy, tragedy or glory on human condition.

All the emotions triggered by experience suffer from the interference of the cultural context of each individual, and if the trigger is too strong, there is the possibility of lack of control on the responses. Paul Ekman (2003), pioneer psychologist on the study of emotions, says that there is a common base of emotional reactions, but the rest endures great influence of the cultural context and this affects the stimulus' interpretations. And the author also mentions that try to exercise control over these emotions won't always work, because when the raised emotion is too strong, the effort makes the interpretation difficult and forces the person to make precipitated decisions that can contribute in a negative way to the experience.

On these contributions, in the same way that Damasio used literature to analyze emotions, in this article, on a less extensive way, it's proposed, unpretentiously, to analyze the artistic intervention Dismaland of Robert Banks, mostly known by the pseudonym Banksy, English street artist. The research contextualizes from the meaning and types of emotions, looking for identify what emerges as it connects with this kind of

expression that comes from the art's world.

Dismaland is a park on Somerset, England, that was installed for a determined period, during August 22th to September 27th, 2015, under the intent to deconstruct the Disney magic and provoke a social critic.

To analyze the correlations between the emotional process, the approaches that come from the design for emotion and the artistic installation, it was chosen a qualitative method of research, anchored by bibliographic research and research on newspapers and periodicals about the subject, and the Dismaland work itself.

The method adopted was developed through a case study based on secondary data since it is an artistic intervention, without any academic bibliographic reference, the search for information was realized through websites, interviews and magazines. These informations were collected across a wide search on internet and selected considering some criterias as, for example, relevance of source. These represent a consistency to comment on the issue, including investigated within the site itself Dismaland, interviews in renowned magazines with the author, Banksy, and material published in journals coming from universities.

The research problem consists in the question: In which way the interaction with the Dismaland park can contribute to justified experiences through the Design for Emotion?

To take care of this problem it starts from a main objective, that it's to comprehend how the interaction with the Dismaland park can contribute to justified experiences through the Design for Emotion. Besides that, it delimitates specific objectives that are described below:

- a Analyze the approaches of the design for emotion;
- b Analyze the Dismaland park;
- c Relate the types of emotional approaches with the people's interactions with the Dismaland park.

To meet the goal "a" a literature was developed with the authors on the topic Emotional Design (section 2). To meet the goal "b" a survey was conducted through websites, magazines and periodicals that have addressed the subject studied, Dismaland, since there is no academic reference on this point (section 3). And to respond the objective "c", a content analysis based on the categories described in the theory was accomplished to see how they were manifested in the studied object (section 4).

This study is divided in understand the approaches of the Emotional Design, analysis of the Dismaland case from Banksy, discussion that relate the types of emotions and interactions emerged on Dismaland, and final considerations, as it's presented below.

The approaches of the Emotional Design

The user's experience with a designed product has as

Figure 1. Jordan's pleasures. Source: Adapted from Jordan (2000).

a result of this interaction an emotion that can be positive, negative or neutral. Besides this emotional aspects being themes of endless studies in Psychology, it was from the decade of 1990 that this subject became also a focus on Design studies. (Tonetto, 2013). The area that cares on investigate the emotions to help on the design of artifacts with the intention of avoid or provoke specific emotions is known as Emotional Design. (Demir et al, 2009). In this perspective, there are three most known approaches, developed by the authors Jordan (1999), Desmet (2002) and Norman (2004).

When the design starts to demand studies that direct the project further than its form and function, it starts to present intangible aspects that are strongly attached to the senses and emotions when linked by people during its interaction with the artifacts. Jordan (2000) is one of the authors that identified this interaction while analyzing the pleasure, which is an emotion, as a result of the use of a product. On that note, he listed four types of pleasures (Figure 1).

The physiological pleasure, that it's quite sensory, people can have it stimulated on the contact with the object through smell, touch, taste, sight or sound. The physiological pleasure can be represented, for example, when entering a cafeteria, and the smell of coffee being so delightful that make a person consume the product, for example. The experience is delightful, therefore to design keeping in mind the physiological pleasure, according to Jordan (2000), is important to ensure the consumption.

The other approach talks about social pleasure, this one related to status, social position. In this case, it's relevant to know the opinion of other people, of society, about what is consumed. Therefore design while contributing to stimulate this feeling of acceptance, of identity, should be considered on Jordan's (2000) point of view.

A third suggestion would refer to psychological pleasure, this one related to the cognitive. The interaction with the artifact is related to its usability.

Figure 2. Norman's levels. Source: Adapted from Norman, 2004.

The result of this relation, if positive, shows a high level of psychological pleasure, and the opposite can occur too. Negative experiences can be extremely nefarious, generating a lower level of pleasure, or even generating no pleasure at all. (Jordan, 2000).

At last, the author says that there's an ideological pleasure related to values and preferences that the human-object interactions generates. Questions arising from moral, culture, experiences, are present when this type of pleasure is stimulated. Another author that engaged on investigate emotions inside design's perspectives was Norman (2004), he assigned three levels of emotional processing: visceral, behavioral and reflective.

The visceral level is the most primitive contact that can be made with an artifact, intimately connected to the product's aesthetics. While interacting with an object, the human being reacts in a pleasant or unpleasant way, and this reaction comes from its first impression of this contact. The behavioral level is connected, on the other hand, to the product's function, the user's interactions will be judged from this perspective. At last, there is the reflective level, mostly related to the meaning that people attribute to products while interacting with them. It's a level mostly associated to culture, to the reflections that are made on the consumptions' process. (Norman, 2004).

The third approach that is presented here brings cognitive evaluations to understand the users' relations with emotions and is a result of Desmet studies (2002). The author utilizes the Appraisals' theory, which comes from psychology, initially on the sixties and more emphatically in the end of the eighties, from the studies of Fridja et al (1989) and adapts it to design. This theory discusses the relation of how emotions are a result of evaluations, which concentrate on a pattern (appraisal), all that reproduced by a stimulus that is related to the users' well-being. The stimulus will provoke a reaction on the person that, if it's positive, will be a pleased one and if it's a negative one, will result on displeasure.

Figure 3 presents the Model of Emotion with Product that Desmet (2002) developed to demonstrate that emotion comes from the evaluation of two elements,

Figure 3. Model of Emotion with Product. Source: Adapted from Desmet, 2002.

the *concern* and the product, being the first one the disposals that usually people bring to the emotional process. The evaluations (appraisals) are the result of this information process revealed on the interaction with the product, through the stimulus (concern). The Appraisal, according to psychology's vision, is an estimative or evaluation of the importance, sense and relevance of certain stimulus that are related to a person's well-being. Essentially, the appraisal of a situation causes an emotional or affective response, based on this evaluation (Frijda, 1986; Lazarus, 1991). This appraisal can be an automatic response for the following question: "What this situation means to my well-being?", if the answer is positive, the person will have a pleasant emotion, but if it's negative, the emotional resolution will be unpleasant. This ponderation helps the individual to recognize the greatness of the experienced situation in a way that an emotion emerges related as a reaction. In that way, each person (taking into account its social and cultural context) will offer a different estimative (or not) facing the same stimulus (Demir; Desmet; Hekkert, 2009).

The case: Banksy's Dismaland

Banksy is a pseudonym of a British graffiti artist, painter, political activist and movie director. His satirical and subversive street art combines black humor and graffiti made with a distinct stencil technique. His work of social and political comments can be found on streets, walls and bridges of cities all around the world. Banksy's work was born in the alternative scene of Bristol, and involved collaborations with other artists and musicians. Being known for his contempt for the government that considers graffiti as vandalism, Banksy exposes his art in public spaces like walls and streets, and even uses objects to show it (Figure 4). Banksy does not sell his work directly, but it's known that art auctioneers tried to sell some of his graffiti in the locals that they were made, letting the problem of how to remove the drawing in the hands of the buyers. (Manco, 2016).

Figure 4. Banksy's art. Source: banksy.co.uk.

Dismaland was an art installation based on *pop-up* books and represents a twisted Disneyland. The project was signed by Banksy, but the entire park has sculptures and interventions from 56 favorite contemporary artist of Banksy, besides presentations of some of the great names of the British music. (Edinboro, 2015). The park was built in a secret way on the city of Somerset in an abandoned resort, called Tropicana, on Weston-super-Mare, England. The name of the park is a pun with "dismal" and Disneyland (Figure 5). It was considered one of the biggest project of the artist so far and, as most of his work and performance, it was created on special secrecy. The residents of the English city thought that the construction of the huge Banksy's decoration was part of a Hollywood movie set. (G1.COM, 2016).

The artistic installations generate more than 20 thousand euros to the local economy, as in tourism companies, hotels and restaurants. The Dismaland ads said: "Are you looking for an alternative for the soulless sugar's coated banality for a day with family? Or just a cheaper place? So this is the place for you – a new chaotic world, where you can run away from the senseless escapism. Instead of a hamburger's tent, we have a museum. Instead of a gift store, we have a library. Well, we have a gift store too...". (Romanzoti, 2016).

Dismaland did a satirical critic to thematic parks. On what all the employees should be grumpy and with no desire to help the guests, the park circulation was thought so that huge lines were accumulated to see the attractions. The games and plays offered on the stands were very hard and barely unbeatable. There was no cleaning service, resulting on piles of garbage and forcing the visitors to detour from the dirt, contributing to the ambience of abandonment – and despair. Besides that, all park areas brought questioning to people about what is fun and the reflection about this experience. The abundance of crossing between modern industry sections, with museums looking for entertain and attractions looking for educate. Banksy took this to the extreme, creating an art gallery with a high level of emotional experience that is an amusement park. (Attractions,

Figure 5. Alternative poster of the park, with ground plan. Source: Google images.

2015).

Types of emotions and the interactions awoken on Dismaland

During the months that the artistic installation Dismaland was available, it provoked all kinds of reactions, as much by people who went to the park as through social media, where it was vastly referenced. Actually the artist and his project partners had in mind exactly that, bring a social critic that provokes discussion and great reflection about values and consumption nowadays. (Edinboro, 2015).

In this context it makes sense the need to explore all emotions that can be trigger while interacting with the park and its diverse proposal. When is established a relationship between Design for Emotion and its theories, it's clear that there is an intention on the project to cause exactly some emotions on the viewer. (Desmet, 2002). If the proposal is to make a social critic, why not stimulate the user to evaluate them, through this experience?

While analyzing the theories that come from the Emotional Design, its perceived on its different approaches, all of them propose to, through the analysis of the interaction between the emotions and some determined artifact, make possible that the designer take into consideration this relation during the project and helps to conceive a product that satisfies the consumer (Desmet, 2002; Jordan, 2000; Norman, 2004).

Under Jordan's perspective (1999, 2000), the physiological pleasure is represented on the contact

Figure 6. Dismaland. Source: Google images.

that people do with Dismaland, when visiting it there's a sensorial experience that register a stimulus to reflection, that could be pleasant or unpleasant, because there is an intention to shock on this visual interaction. The social pleasure is distinguished by questioning society, knowing what they think about what is really associated on the installations spread on the park. While the psychological pleasure is distinguished by generating a cognitive stimulus on who interacts with the proposal offered by Dismaland. The great reflection of Disney's antithesis, the magic and perfect world of fairytales.

Looking through Norman's optic (2004), it's possible to associate the park to visceral, behavioral and reflective emotional levels, which are stimulated on the interactions that were made during the contact with the artistic intervention. The visceral exposes the emotions related to the park's aesthetics, that many times can remind disorder, dirt and grotesque look, but the project planned precisely that, to shock the public. The behavioral level of this approach is intimately connected to the product's usability, on this aspect the utility of Dismaland is associated to causing commotion, stimulate emotions that perceive what is behind the work. And this question is also close to Norman's reflective level that suggests a project that instigates people to expand their emotions on this interaction. There is a latent meaning on Dismaland that emerges from the search to liquid consumerism, the life form that the XX century allowed itself and caused the sustainable current losses. Emotions about how to establish a social and cultural reflection are stimulated by this bias.

Yet the approaches investigated by Desmet (2002) can be assigned on the Dismaland project as the

interactions' exploration listed on Figure 3. The stimulus (concerns) caused by the contact with the product (park) generate evaluations that create emotions. In this case, the designers involved on the Dismaland project guaranteed an experience that had a critic, and even uncomfortable, unpleasant nature, on the user so that it would have a reflection about the role of society in the world. To provoke this stimulus would be necessary to generate questioning on people. The negative emotion in this sense was necessary to reach the project objective, related to its social critic.

And through the Appraisals' theory optic and through Ekman's vision (2003), Dismaland was the result of a very well planned project by Banksy, to provoke this negative emotions and with that generate questioning, but each person who went to the park received the same stimulus, but the deliberation about the emotional response takes into consideration the individual context of each guest. The perceptions of discomfort provoked in all park's spaces, helped on the affective negative responses (Fridja, 1986) as discomfort and even despair, as reported by some people that had the opportunity to experience the intervention. But also, other guests liked and remained for a long time on the park, participating on all offered events. They told that they felt pleasure with the negative emotions and that were comfortable with all the questioning that were stimulated. In this way, the cultural and social context of each person affected the evaluation of the experience with the park attractions.

Final considerations

This article proposed to bring a brief discussion about the theories that talk about emotion and the artistic intervention created by Banksy, the Dismaland park. In this analysis were referenced the users' interactions

with the park and what types of emotions could be awakened so it would generate a social critic of today's social values like consumerism and sustainability.

While being taken away to a different experience, the user was stimulated to reflect about the aspects related to culture nowadays. The interaction with Dismaland was the antithesis of the interactions that occur on the other amusement parks, because it generates some oddness and, in some cases, discomfort, because of works of high deconstruction impact similar to already existent works.

The theories that come from the Emotional Design relate emotional stimulus associated to the interactions that people are predisposed to do with products and services. According to one of these theories already referenced here, the Appraisals' theory project (Desmet, 2000), it's possible to awake emotions as much positives as negatives, during the project creation. Analyzing under this optic, Banksy and the artists invited to develop this installation, were responsible precisely to provoke negative emotions on the park guests so they would be lead to certain social questioning. In this sense, they were successful, because even who felt pleasure while enjoying all the possibilities that the park offered, was stimulated to wander through the park exactly because of emotions that would guarantee a more critic look on the work. Others, therefore, reported that the interaction with Dismaland provoked such displeasure that they preferred to leave the installation and not participate in all events.

If the intention was to shock, it was achieved. Banksy, on the other hand, affirmed on interviews that he could have been too gentle on the provocations established there, but during the project's elaboration, looking through the Emotional Design perspective, the emotions were stimulated intentionally. There is achievement on a project that can connect this emotional or affective stimulus through the evaluation that the users establish on their relations with the products-services (Fridja, 1986).

Therefore, it's considered that the Dismaland project was successful, because it stimulated people to question themselves about: "*What this situation means to my wellbeing?*". The answer could be as much positive as negative, generating delightful or not delightful emotional experiences, respectively. The important thing on this context was precisely to cause a commotion that would bring questioning about society and current lifestyle. (Demir; Desmet; Hekkert, 2009).

It became clear that the same stimulus can or cannot generate different perceptions in this experience, so it's important to address that different social and cultural contexts influence on these evaluations. But being good or bad, we can't disregard that this project turned people's experience in a memorable event.

Given the relevance of the object studied and the lack of academic research around the work, this is an initial study of the artistic intervention, Dismaland,

which encourages a future work from this one. The suggestion is that in a next step of this research, the study will not be based only on secondary data, it will contemplate an approach to end-users. It is believed that, doing this, will be able to conduct a deeply discussion the emotions aroused by the intervention.

References

- Attractions. Attractions Management Magazine. VOL20 Q4. <<http://www.attractionsmanagement.com>>. Acesso: Dez, 2015.
- Damasio, A. (1996). O erro de Descartes: emoção, razão e cérebro humano. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras.
- Damasio, A. (2000). O Mistério da Consciência: do corpo e das emoções do conhecimento de si. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras.
- Demir, E.; Desmet, P. M. A.; Hekkert, P. (2009). Appraisal Patterns of Emotions in Human-Product Interaction. *International Journal of Design*.
- Desmet, P. (2002). Designing emotions. Delft, The Netherlands. Tese de Doutorado. Delft University of Technology.
- Edinboro, Campus Media. (2015). Banksy's Dismaland enlisting an Edinboro touch. *The Spectator*. Edinboro University.
- Ekman P. (2003) Emotions Revealed: Recognizing Faces and Feelings to Improve Communication and Emotional Life. In: <<http://www.cebtm.net/CEBtM%20Sources/Emotions%20Revealed%201-4.pdf>>. Acesso: 25 jan 2016.
- Fridja, N. H., Kuipers, P.; Ter Schure, E. (1989) Relations among emotion, appraisal, and emotional action readiness. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol.57, n.2.
- Fridja, N. H. (1986). *The Emotions*. Cambridge, UK: Columbia University Press.
- G1.COM. (2016). <<http://g1.globo.com/pop-arte/noticia/2015/08/banksy-inaugura-dismaland-parque-para-anarquistas-principiantes.html>>. Acesso Jan, 2016.
- James, W. (1884). What is an emotion? *Mind*, 9, 188-205.
- Jordan, P. (2000). *Designing pleasurable products*. London, Taylor & Francis.
- Jordan, P. (1999). Inclusive design. In: W.S. Green; P.W. Jordan (eds.), *Human factors in product design: Current practice and future trends*. London, Taylor & Francis, p. 171-181.
- Lazarus, R.S. (1991). *Emotional and Adaptation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Manco, T. (2016). In: <<http://www.tristanmanco.com/2012/11/09/the-rake/>>. Acesso: Jan, 2016.

Norman, D.A. (2004). *Emotional Design: Why we love (or hate) everyday things*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

Romanzoti, N. (2016). In: <<http://hypescience.com/a-disneyland-de-banksy-e-um-pesadelo/>>. Acesso: Jan, 2016.

Scherer, K. R. (2005) What are emotions? And how can they be measured? *Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales*, v. 44, n. 4, p. 695- 729,

Tonetto, L. (2013). Os designers na projeção das emoções. In: *Design to Branding Magazine/GAD*, vol.09, São Paulo.